

Investigating the use of Open Education Resources (OERs) in Filipino in the context of emergency remote learning

Fabian, Khristin,
Esperanza, Peter
Abacan, Ray

UHI Perth College | Khristin.fabian.perth@uhi.ac.uk
Barstow Community College | pesperanza@barstow.edu
Enderun Colleges | ray.abacan@enderuncolleges.com

FORMAT

Paper

ABSTRACT

During the enforced lockdown in the Philippines due to Covid-19, teachers and students were at sea due to the sudden transition to online or distance learning. Many teachers did not have adequate access to technology and teaching resources to allow them to teach at home. The use of open educational resources (OERs) is one of the strategies to bridge the resource gap. However, adoption of OERs is complicated and presents many challenges (Wang & Towey, 2017). Parallel to the resource gap is the language gap. Previous research found that language of instruction has an effect in mathematics performance (Bernardo, 2002). Many teachers use Filipino alongside English when explaining math concepts (Bravo-Sotelo, 2020). However, during the transition to online learning, teacher-student interaction has been limited. At the start of the pandemic, few math resources were readily available in Filipino (DepEdCommons, 2020) so some teachers translated the English resources to Filipino to help those doing remote learning (Roman, 2020). The current multi-method study aims to investigate how teachers adopt the use of OERs (video resources) in their teaching practice and investigate whether there's a difference in math scores between those who use the English version of the videos and those who used the ones in Filipino. A total of 208 Grade 9 and 463 Grade 10 students and 25 teachers took part in the study. The teachers and their respective students were grouped into English and Filipino groups. For 10 weeks, the teachers and the students in the Filipino group used the math video resources in Filipino and the English group used the English versions. Following that period, the teachers were free to use either version of the videos. All videos were developed by one of the researchers of this study. The teachers were free to adapt the videos as they see fit and were also free to redistribute the videos to their students in whichever medium was convenient. To compare student performance between groups, students completed a pre-test at the start of the study and a post-test 10 weeks later. Teacher interviews were conducted six months after the start of the study. Feedback on the resources has been positive. Teachers found the videos useful particularly the availability of both English and Filipino videos on the same topic. They used the resources to supplement remote-learning modules (offline learning) and as part of their synchronous sessions. However, some topics within the curriculum does not have a corresponding resource or the resource isn't a good fit in terms of depth and breadth of explanation and on occasion in terms of its approach/strategy to teaching a particular topic. An independent t-test to compare the student gain scores between the Filipino and English group found significant differences. For both grade levels, the Filipino groups had higher gain scores than the English groups (G9: $t=4.146$, $p<.001$, $d=.57$; G10: $t=2.170$, $p<.031$, $d=.22$). These results raise the need to develop more math videos in Filipino rather than simply adopting already available English math OERs. Future work needs further mapping of OERs with curricular offerings.

KEYWORDS

Open Educational Resources (OERs); mathematics education; remote learning; online learning

REFERENCES

- Bernardo, A. B. (2002). Language and mathematical problem solving among bilinguals. *The Journal of Psychology, 136*(3), 283-297.
- Bravo-Sotelo, K. P. (2020). Exploring the Tagalog-English Code-Switching Types Used for Mathematics Classroom Instruction. *IAFOR Journal of Education, 8*(1), 47-64.
- DepEdCommons (2020). DepED Commons. <https://commons.deped.gov.ph> accessed 12 July 2020
- Roman, A. (2021). Experiences of Teachers on Using Modular Distance Learning (MDL) in Teaching Mathematics During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Southeast Asian Journal of Science and Technology, 6*(2 (SI)), 78-86.
- Wang, T., & Towey, D. (2017, December). Open educational resource (OER) adoption in higher education: Challenges and strategies. In *2017 IEEE 6th International Conference on Teaching, Assessment, and Learning for Engineering (TALE)*(pp. 317-319). IEEE.